

Synthesis of Some New 2-Aryl-3-Hetaryl-4(3H) Quinazolones

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2-Aryl (alkyl)-benzoxazin-4-ones (I, R=CH₃, C₆H₅, C₆H₄CH₃, *p*-NO₂C₆H₄) are condensed with 2-amino hetaryls (pyridyl, pyrimidyl, thiazolyl), 1 & 2-amino anthraquinones, *p*-amino acetophenone and 1,2-diamines like ethylene diamine and *o*-phenylene diamine. The products are obtained in excellent yields and are characterised by infrared and elemental analysis.

THE quinazolone chemistry with its diverse biological properties like CNS depressant^{1,2}, anticonvulsant^{3,4}, muscle relaxant^{5,6}, and antiviral⁷ has got much importance in recent years. The structural modification at the 2-aryl moiety has shown excellent results in pharmacology. The present work aims at synthesizing a number of quinazolone derivatives supposed to be potentially active.

The reported⁸ literature procedure was followed for the synthesis of quinazolones and all the products were characterised by infrared and elemental analysis. In all the benzoxazinones the carbonyl of the lactone ring gave a peak around 1680 cm⁻¹. In contrast, when the benzoxazinones react with amines, the nitrogen inserted products showed intense peak at 1650-1660 cm⁻¹ region indicating the presence of an amide carbonyl. As a part of our programme to synthesize some new heterocyclics with a bridgehead nitrogen atom particularly at the 3,4-positions, the benzoxazinones were allowed to react with simple 1,2-diamines like *o*-phenylene diamine and ethylene diamine. To our surprise it was observed that out of the two

a = R=CH₃; b = R=C₆H₅; c = R=C₆H₄CH₃; d = R=*p*-NO₂C₆H₄
 X = II, 2-Pyridyl; III, 2-Pyrimidyl;
 IV, 2-Thiazolyl; V, *p*-carboxyphenyl;
 VI, *p*-methyl carboxyphenyl (*p*-C₆H₄CH₃COOH);
 VII, *p*-acetophenyl; VIII, 1-anthraquinonyl;
 IX, 2-anthraquinonyl;

Scheme 1

available amino groups, only one takes part in the insertion. This finding was supported by the positive test for amino group (azo dye test in case of *o*-phenylene diamine) and the appearance of a peak at 3350 cm⁻¹ (NH stretching) in system X and XI (Scheme 2). Construction of a five membered ring is precluded probably due to steric reasoning. In contrast however, systems like *p*-phenylene diamine,

Scheme 2

benzidine where both the amino functions are far apart gave products of the type XII and XIV. Additionally when two molar quantities of the benzoxazinones were taken and allowed to react with one molar quantity of the amines, the structure of the products dramatically changed to XIII and XV (Scheme 3). These observations led us to infer that nitrogen atoms of both the amino functions were taken up in the insertion processes.

Scheme 3

Further, the benzoxazinones on reaction with amines like 1-aminoanthraquinone, 2-aminoanthraquinone and *p*-amino acetophenone gave crystalline coloured products.

Experimental

All melting points were taken in open capillaries and are uncorrected. The IR spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 137 spectrophotometer. TLC were run over silica gel plates.

Preparation of 2-R-benzoxazinones :

Acetyl anthranil I ($R=CH_3$) was prepared following the procedure available in literature⁹, m.p. 79-80° (lit.⁹ 80-81°). The other 2-R-benzoxazinones I ($R=C_6H_5$, $C_6H_5CH_2$ and $p-NO_2C_6H_4$) were prepared following literature procedure⁸. I, $R=C_6H_5$, m.p. 121° (lit.¹⁰, m.p. 123°), yield 80%; $R=C_6H_5CH_2$, m.p. 165°, 83%; $R=p-NO_2C_6H_4$, m.p. 200° (lit.¹⁰, m.p. 203°), 78%.

Reaction of 2-R-benzoxazinones with amines— General Procedure :

Equimolar (0.01 mol) mixture of 2-R-benzoxazinone and the amine was taken in pyridine (20 ml) and the solution was heated under reflux for 6 hr. Then the reaction mixture was cooled to room temperature, poured into ice water and neutralised with conc. HCl when the solid product separated out. The solid was filtered, washed with cold water several times and dried. The crude product was crystallised from alcohol or alcohol-water mixture. Only in two cases of 1,4-diamines (*p*-phenylene diamine and benzidine) the benzoxazinone and the amine were taken in 2 : 1 molar ratios to obtain the products X and XII respectively following the usual procedure. All the compounds were obtained in high yields (50-80%) and gave satisfactory C, H and N analysis. Compound II a, b, c and d had melting points 176°, 113°, 178° and 232° respectively. Compound III a, b, c and d had m.ps 170°, 155°, 183° and 220°; Compound IV a, b, c and d had m.ps 178°, 218°, 179° and 200°; Compound V a, b, c and d

had m.ps 261-63°, 159-60°, 168° and 190°; Compound VI a, b, c and d had m.ps 253°, 161°, 145° and 189°; Compound VII a, b, c and d had m.ps 245°, 110°, 165-67° and 185°; Compound VIII a, b, c and d had m.ps 262°, 185° and 190°; Compound IX a, b, c and d had m.ps 162-63°, 136-37°, 180° and 201°; Compound X a, b, c and d had m.ps 170°, 239°, 175° and 201°; Compound XI a, b, c and d had m.ps 180°, 85°, 186° and 235°; Compound XII a, b, c and d had m.ps 161°, 186°, 160° and 103°; Compound XIII a, b, c and d had m.ps 167°, 166°, 175° and 115°; Compound XIV a, b, c and d had m.ps 275°, 255°, 239° and 205° and Compound XV a, b, c and d had m.ps 215°, 241°, 168° and 220° respectively.

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